

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B282
Date: 15 April 2007
Take Off: 15:06:50
Landing: 18:41:55
Flight Time: 3h35m05

Campaign: IASI - Houston Pollution Plume Sortie

Operating Area: Houston area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jon Taylor	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	Met Office
7	CCM2 / Core Chem	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
8	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
9	SWS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
10	MARSS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
11	Wet Neph / PSAP2	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
12	AMS 1	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
13	AMS 2	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
14	Mission Scientist 2	Stuart Newman	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 3	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B282 Track 15-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B282

Date: 15 April 2007

Project: IASI (Houston Plume)

Location: North of Houston and Gulf of Mexico

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
144203		start up	-.26 kft	358	29'36.05N 95'10.06W
145554	145908	Pirouette 1	-.25 kft	013	start
145728		ASP	-.25 kft	268	open
150650		T/O	0.61 kft	008	
150650	150857	Profile 1	0.87 - 1.7 kft	032	15:06:50 int
150913	151708	Profile 1	1.7 - 9.7 kft	048	
152929	153634	Profile 2	9.7 - 2.5 kft	008	
153808	160033	Run 1.1	2.5 - 2.4 kft	050	
160250	162448	Run 1.2	2.4 - 2.5 kft	247	
161855		Tapes	2.4 kft	246	changed
162448	163227	Profile 3	2.5 - 9.7 kft	247	
165833	170913	Profile 4	10.7 - -.27 kft	192	
170913	171237	Profile 5	-.27 - 2.5 kft	083	
171237	171626	Repositioning	2.5 - 1.1 kft	083	Runs 2.1,3.1 & 4.1 & P5
171626	173930	Run 5.1	1.1 - 1.2 kft	087	
174801		Tapes	3.2 kft	332	Changed
180017	180352	Profile 6	4.2 - 1.1 kft	239	
180352	180731	Run 6.1	1.1 kft	223	
180859	181641	Run 6.2	1.1 kft	046	
183047	184155	Profile 7	4.4 - -.19 kft	308	
184155		Land	-.20 kft	322	
184416	184706	Pirouette 2	-.19 kft	173	
185023		ASP	-.19 kft	358	closed
185015		Shutdown	-.19 kft	358	29'36.05N 95'10.05W

B282 Track 15-APR-07

UFC / FFC

meeting time to be decided in flight

FliteStar 9.170

Confirm have SATCOM Contact 281 280 5382

Houston Center
 verify position on Sub-plane
 TRANSIT TO D

time to be emitted 17:13:34
 PL
 16:02:30
 17:15:08 PL
 TAKE OFF/P1 - 15:06:50
 LAND/P7 - 18:41:55

Brief
 2:30

15:47:45 - TWC off
 Strike light on
 Run 1.2 16:02:50

h-shop
 optic
 optic
 1

HOME

Run 2.2

Sortie Brief

Flight B282

15th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Jon Taylor

Briefing: 0800L

Take off: 1000L

Land: 1500L

Aim: To measure aerosol physics and chemistry in the outflow from Houston and its evolution with time. The sortie is similar to those conducted during AMPEP/VISURB, to measure the entire plume leaving the Houston city area and ideally to observe the transformation of the plume downwind of the source region.

Location: Immediately upwind of Houston and downwind of the urban area. BAe 146 will follow fixed points as defined below.

Weather conditions: Extensive boundary layer cloud is not desirable; mid and upper level cloud is not detrimental.

Key instruments: AMS, CO, O₃, PSAP, PCASP, nephelometer (ideally wet neph), CO₂ tuneable diode, CPC. **AMS requires 4 hours pump down time and 1-2 hours post flight.**

Fixed Points:

Fixed point A: start of upwind SLR (30°48' N, 95°10' W)

Fixed point B: end of upwind SLR (31°30' N, 93°45' W)

Fixed point D: start of first downwind SLR (28°05'N, 96° 05'W)

Fixed point E: end of first downwind SLR (28° 05'N, 91° 20'W)

Fixed point F: start of second downwind SLR (27° 20'N, 91° 20' W).

Fixed point G: end of second downwind SLR (27° 20'N, 96° 05'W)

1. Take off, profile to FL100, transit to position A for upwind leg and undertake a profile descent to minimum safe altitude (3500ft) to point A (30 mins)
2. Start straight and level run from A to B at a level in boundary layer (25 mins)
3. Turn and position for next run (5 mins)
4. Start straight and level run from B to A at a level in boundary layer (25 mins)
5. Profile ascent to 8000ft on transit to point D
6. Profile descent to point D at 50ft (40mins)
7. Ascent to 2000ft followed by Straight and level to point E (70 mins)
8. Straight and level run to point F (15mins)
9. Straight and level run from point F to point G (70mins)
10. Straight and level run from point G to D (15mins)
11. Profile ascent to 8000ft from point D on transit to Ellington (30mins)

**Mission Scientists De-brief – Flight B282 Houston Plume.
Sunday 15th April 2007
Jonathan P Taylor.**

Summary – an unsuccessful sortie due to poor advection of the Houston plume off the coast due to light winds.

The aim of the sortie was to study the pollution from Houston. The sortie started with a series of two runs North of Houston to characterise the background aerosol conditions. The inversion was at 5500ft; there were two distinct plumes of pollution from sources further north but both of these were only a few miles across and were not seen on the AMS.

Following the upwind runs we re-positioned to South of Houston over the Gulf of Mexico. Initially the run was positioned 80nm off the coast but no Houston plume was detected. We tried a run just 20nm off the coast but once again no significant plume was detected.

The sortie was aborted as the pollution was not found. On return to Houston it was evident that there was pollution immediately over the city but that the winds were not strong enough to advect this off the coast.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. Taylor

IASI - HOUSTON PLUME FLIGHT

Flight No **B282**.....
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Date 15 APR 07.....

Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
145508		Surf.			Start of Runette 1 per BBLs
		Surf.			End of Runette
150703	P1				Start of Runette on T104
	P1	FC100			End of Runette
					Totally cloudless conditions.
					Distinct aerosol layer visible on horizon
					PCASP voltage a bit low + worry in C1.
152929					Start P2.
					Inversion 5500ft.
					Blue = 15.05 23.05 m ⁻¹
					Green = 15.88 m ⁻¹
					Red = 10.9 m ⁻¹
153634					End of P2 <u>UPWIND OF HOUSTON</u>
153804	R1.1	2700ft.	057		Start Run 1.1 at A wind 326° 7-9 m/s ⁻¹
					RGB read 9 chgs to 1546 then stabilize
					Some v-shallow inv on inversion top.
					CNC chgs to 2700/cm ⁻³ but
					large peak at 1546 of 70,000/cm ⁻³
1559.					CNC 7 m/s ⁻¹ .
160023		2700ft.			End of Run 1.1 at B

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Houston Run

J. Taylor

Flight No **B...282**

Date **...15 APR 07...**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
160349	R1-2	2800ft	249		st Run 1-2 towards A.
160430					st left large peak in CNC Hdg West.
1615					Peak again in CNC up to 87000 we are dominated by 2 forms!
161951					out of plume.
162431					Small plume in CNC + ROR.
162608	R1-2 P3	2700ft	246		End Run 1-2 + Start of P3 PSAP ≈ 17 μl in 1 day layer
163229	P3	10000ft	245		End of P3
	P4	500ft			End of P4 at 500ft. Stop P5 2800ft too high and by 1 day layer plume.
	P6	2800ft ↓			Descent to 1900ft 1900 too high by 1600ft
171626	R5-1	1600ft			Run 5-1 dominated by Houston
	R5-1	1500ft			End of Run due to low reflection levels
180017	P6	4500ft ↓			Stop P6 to position closer to coast descending to 1600ft.
180352	P6 R6	1600ft	224		Stop R6 Hdg west in plume of aerosol. 20nm off coast Dr to
180744	R6	1600ft	224		End of R6

B282

Houston
6-5ppbv.

Run 1-1

O₃ ~ 45

CO ~ 160-180

NO ~ 0.6 0.87 } by end of run

NO₂ ~ 1.2 2.15 }

NO_x ~ 1.70 upto 2.2 up to 3 by end of run

Backgd ↑ over run

Run 1-2

3-5 kft ↓ NO_x ↑ O₃

Houston Centre

+ 1 281 230 5552

No channel with available Code 34.

1500 ft.

1st run downstream NO_x values ~ 0.5ppb higher

CO 180-200 ppbv.

O₃ 54 ppbv.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST 2: STUART NEWMAN

Flight No **B.282**
FAAM © 2004

Date **15/4/07**

Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
150743	/P1				TAKE-OFF
					Interrupted profile climb in odd direction at first (air traffic)
1516	end P1	FL100			Band of pollution on horizon
1528					Transit to pt A, windspeed $\approx 15 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ at 3000ft on ascent, N'ly with slightly W'ly component
152929	P2	FL100 ↓			
1535		4000'			Neph ^{blue} scatt increasing $> 10 \text{ m}^{-1}$
153634	end P2				
153808	R1.1	2400'			Wind 8 ms^{-1} at 340°
1551					Neph up to $\sim 40 \text{ m}^{-1}$, combination from 2D about increase in signal
1558					Approaching Cu clouds
160033	end R1.1				CNC peak here $\sim 70000 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
160344	R1.2				
162448	end R1 PROFILE	2400' ↑			
165833	P ↓	FL100 ↓			Inversion 3400'
1713					Now above inversion at 2400'
171623	R5.1	1400'			
1735		1400'			Not picking up plume, low concs
1739	end R5.1				About early due to lack of aerosol loading
180017	P6	↓			Working closer to coast
180352	R6.1	1450'			Bigger NO_x , CNC, neph signals
180731	end R6.1				

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B282 **T/O:** 150650
Date of flight: 15/04/07 **Land:** 184155

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	No data	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	N	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	N	<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B282
Date of Flight: 15/04/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 -> 50000 2 -> 10000 3-> 1000 Vol flow rate = 0.8 150500 184500
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas Y = X+1 = _tas_pcas3
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Data present in tas_pcas3 Merged OK?


```

14:20:58.68 --- - - - -
14:20:58.68 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
14:20:58.68 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                               tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
14:20:58.68 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B282
14:20:58.68 --- - - - -
14:21:50.49 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
14:22:38.43 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
14:22:38.62 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:47:32.88 --- - - - - *** time check
13:47:45.72 --- - - - - *** time set manually as about time failed
13:48:04.00 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:48:08.51 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:48:12.61 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:48:38.65 SWS - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
13:48:46.04 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.
13:48:50.01 SWS - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
13:48:53.96 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
13:48:58.54 USH - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
13:49:03.01 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
13:49:05.92 LSH - - - 990 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
13:49:08.27 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:49:08.27 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:49:08.28 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:49:11.92 SWS - - - - Idling
13:49:12.69 USH - - - - Idling
13:49:15.53 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:49:15.53 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:49:19.33 LSH - - - - Idling
13:52:21.96 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:52:22.18 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:52:22.24 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:52:25.32 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:52:25.72 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:52:32.30 LSH - - - - Idling
14:39:17.36 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:39:24.02 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:39:24.16 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:39:24.65 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:39:26.97 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:39:27.68 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:39:34.99 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:39:54.52 SWS - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
14:40:01.02 SWS - - - 300 NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
14:40:05.81 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
14:40:12.93 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
14:40:18.37 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
14:40:24.91 USH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
14:40:30.60 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:40:30.70 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:40:31.29 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:40:36.79 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:40:37.52 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:40:38.54 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:40:41.62 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:46:05.26 --- - - - - *** SWS to 0 deg in prep for pitouette
14:47:11.37 SWS - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 350ms.
14:47:15.20 SWS - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:47:20.35 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:47:28.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:47:35.47 SWS - - - - Idling
14:47:36.54 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:47:43.70 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:47:51.64 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:51:27.47 USH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
14:51:29.54 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:51:37.48 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.

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14:56:01.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of pirouette 1
14:59:06.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** End of pirouette 1
14:59:35.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWs head aft for t/o
15:19:51.69	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
15:20:31.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** In transit/profile SWS head to 6deg fore in prep for run1.1
15:28:42.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:28:52.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:29:28.45	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:29:40.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:29:41.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:29:44.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:29:49.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:29:50.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:29:52.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:30:24.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** Sticky shutter on LWS not sorted - in profile descent
15:31:11.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** Above should read NOW sorted ie it's working
15:33:38.72	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:33:41.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:46.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:22.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.1
15:38:27.44	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
15:38:29.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:37.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:11.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:12.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:12.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:17.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:20.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:22.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:05.02	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
15:47:08.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:47:16.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:47.64	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:48:53.53	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:48:56.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:01.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:06.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:06.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:06.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:50:12.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:14.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:16.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:20.13	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:51:22.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:51:27.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:08.79	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
15:54:14.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:22.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:45.99	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
15:55:51.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:51.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:52.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:57.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:59.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:56:02.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:00:51.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run under shallow cu
16:02:15.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.2
16:02:25.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:25.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:25.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:30.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:33.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:36.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:52.49	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:03:31.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** under shallow cul
16:04:18.66	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.

16:04:22.44	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
16:04:33.21	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
16:04:40.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:41.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:41.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:46.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:46.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:51.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:32.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** over 7/8 forrest
16:09:46.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:46.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:46.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:52.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:52.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:53.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:09:56.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:02.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** over the central lake
16:11:52.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** back over forrested area
16:13:44.02	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:13:48.32	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
16:13:52.57	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
16:14:04.22	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
16:14:07.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:07.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:07.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:13.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:15.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:17.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:20.81	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
16:14:23.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:31.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:06.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:09.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:12.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:19:14.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:14.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:19:23.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:16.20	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:20:25.85	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:20:31.68	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
16:20:42.54	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
16:20:48.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:48.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:48.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:53.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:53.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:58.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:28.87	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
16:21:35.34	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
16:21:40.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:21:45.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:54.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** presume more shallow cu
16:22:52.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** Ignore last remark - aware sws is pointing down
16:24:43.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** over river
16:24:54.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1.2
16:25:21.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** in profile climb
16:26:25.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:26.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:26.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:30.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:31.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:36.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:57:39.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS head to 114 deg aft for start of run
16:58:27.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:58:27.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:58:27.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:58:32.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:58:32.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

16:58:37.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:02:40.34	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
17:02:54.14	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
17:02:59.35	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
17:03:08.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:03:08.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:03:08.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:03:14.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:03:17.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:03:19.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:38.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
17:12:51.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:12:51.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:12:52.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:12:57.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:13:00.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:13:02.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:14:53.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head still at 114 aft
17:15:39.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run proper
17:16:06.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** run abandoned
17:16:27.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
17:18:22.04	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
17:18:24.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:18:32.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:03.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 134 deg aft
17:20:08.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:08.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:08.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:13.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:16.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:18.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:26.54	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:20:29.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:37.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:20.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 154 aft
17:22:32.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:32.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:32.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:38.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:40.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:42.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:39.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 174 aft
17:24:54.76	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:24:59.38	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
17:25:03.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:03.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:03.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:08.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:12.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:12.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:13.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:27:22.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 166 f
17:27:48.37	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
17:27:54.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:27:54.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:27:54.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:27:59.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:02.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:05.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:59.75	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
17:29:01.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:10.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:11.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:58.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 146 f
17:30:23.62	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
17:30:28.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:29.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:29.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:34.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

17:30:37.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:39.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:06.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head repositioned to 146 f as prev drifting
17:32:10.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:10.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:11.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:16.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:18.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:21.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:34:32.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 126 f
17:36:10.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws now stopped drifting due to operator innovation
17:36:15.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:15.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:15.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:21.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:36:24.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:36:26.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:38:23.42	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:38:39.09	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
17:38:42.19	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
17:38:47.38	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
17:38:53.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:38:53.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:38:53.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:38:58.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:39:01.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:39:03.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:39:39.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run called
17:41:26.28	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
17:41:29.62	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
17:41:32.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:41:36.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:45:13.53	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
17:45:18.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:45:28.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:48:04.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:48:05.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:48:05.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:48:09.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:48:13.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:48:16.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:53:58.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** last few mins spent unwinding sws head.
17:54:17.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** Will not stay in position without assistance for
17:55:56.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** angles 30-90 deg fore & 120-140 deg fore
17:56:06.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** will hold in all aft angles
17:56:23.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** back to 6 deg fore
17:56:27.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:27.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:27.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:31.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:36.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:37.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:37.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:02:37.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:02:38.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:02:38.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:02:42.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:02:45.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:02:49.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:03:56.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** strat of run 6
18:04:24.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 114 aft
18:04:26.10	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
18:04:31.09	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
18:04:33.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:33.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:34.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

18:04:38.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:04:39.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:04:42.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:04:44.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:09.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:09.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:09.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:13.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:17.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:19.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:29.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** accidental dark all
18:06:48.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 174 aft
18:07:04.37	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
18:07:08.17	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
18:07:13.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:07:13.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:07:13.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:07:18.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:18.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:21.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:24.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:47.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** run abandoned
18:08:07.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 114 in preparation
18:09:08.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 6.2
18:09:12.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:09:12.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:09:13.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:09:17.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:09:21.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:09:23.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:11:33.03	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:11:45.15	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
18:12:12.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:12:12.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:12:12.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:12:17.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:12:20.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:12:23.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:14:16.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to 166 f
18:14:27.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:14:27.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:14:27.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:14:31.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:14:35.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:14:37.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:14:46.60	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 400ms.
18:14:55.54	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
18:14:59.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:15:08.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:16:33.69	---	-	-	-	-	***
18:16:33.80	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:17:09.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** run abandoned
18:20:48.98	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
18:20:56.86	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
18:21:09.92	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:21:12.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:21:12.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:21:12.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:21:16.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:21:20.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:21:22.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:21:43.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head to aft for landing
18:43:24.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head 0 degrees
18:43:30.96	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
18:43:35.62	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
18:43:42.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:43:42.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:43:42.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:43:47.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

18:43:51.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:43:52.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:43:52.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:44:19.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of pirouette 2
18:47:08.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of pirouette
18:47:16.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of science
18:47:46.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:47:50.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:47:52.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:48:01.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:48:05.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:48:08.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
18:48:25.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** d

* WARNING, ALL TIMES 1 HOUR AHEAD GMT *

ARIES flight log		Flight: 3282	page 1 of
Date: 15/4/07	Operator(s): Joss	Res:	Gain A: B:
Loc./Notes: ASI HOUSTON CAMPAIGN			

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Sshr	HBB	CBB	Comments
1456							started data recording
161918	Transit						Run COLD/HOT cal (1:04) used here for higher res temps.
1634	PV						Redfd cal
163823	R1-1						Cal Cals for bands trans temp
164434	R1-1						cold/hot cal script. 71.03°C 30-42°C
164640	R1-1	360/1	Zen. open		70.6	30.47	3mins
165002	R1-1				70.06	30.71	cold/hot cal script
165141	R1-1	240/1	Had				
165325	R1-1	240/1	Had				cls
165534	R1-1				70.96	30.8	Hot/cold cal.
165709	R1-1	240/1	Had				open
							Had
165947	R1-1 end						70.62 30.86. CAL cold/hot.
170157	R1-2 start				70.82	31.15	Hot/cold cal.
170329	R1-2	480	Had		70.77	30.72	exp had 480 coadded scans!
170443	R1-2	480/1	Had				cls
170848	R1-2				70.92	30.56	cold/hot cal.
171010	R1-2	480/1	Had				?
171235	R1-2				70.96	31.0	cold/hot cal.
171400	R1-2	240/1	Zen. open				Zenith with SWS
1717	R1-2	360/1	Had				open
171846	R1-2	L			70.88	31.19	CAL cold/hot
172009	R1-2	480/1	Had				
172414	R1-2						CU cold/hot
							Had
							PTO

z
N

360
480

uses!

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 2 9 2

page 2 of

Date: 15/04/06

Operator(s): JOSS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2B:2

Loc./Notes: All times +1 hours on GMT.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

120
200
1

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
171238	R				70-62	30-68	cal cold/hot. run aborted
171542	R						cal cold/hot. " " "
171700	RS.1			clsd	70-91	30-41	cal cold/hot. Used for bright sources
171851	RS.1	600/1	Zen	open			long Zen view.
172442	RS.1				70-66	31-32	cold/hot cal. used for
172559	RS.0	600/1	Zen			30-32	
173129	RS.1				71-0	31-32	
173553	RS.1						
173642	RS.1			clsd	71-03	30-37	cold/hot cal.
173817	RS.1	480/1	Nad	clsd			Shape Nad view finished 173822
173946	end RS.1		CAL	clsd	71-06	30-28	cal/hot cal.
174307			CAL	clsd	71-06		70-89 30-31 cold/hot cal.
174452		360/1	clsd	Nad			Looking down
174815		240/1	open	Zen			
175022			clsd	cal.	71-02	31-02	cold/hot cal.
175152		480/1	clsd	Nad			Nadir view.
175548			cal.	clsd	71-17	30-91	cold/hot cal.
180340	R6-1	CAL	cal	clsd			70-85 30-69 °C for cal.
180512	R6-1	600/1	Zen	open			Finish early @ 180746
180750	end R6.1	CAL	cal	clsd	71-1	30-8	2
180920	R6-2	600/1	Nad	clsd			Good look down.
181614	R6-2				71-04	30-76	cal
181856			END	DATA			

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	15/04/07	Flight	B282	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	JIAVEX		
Departure	1500		Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on			at time	1255ish		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	282	Cold	280		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time			
Scan indication		Monitor	•		Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software			at time	NA		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor			Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	13:30:18		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	328	Cold	280	
			and rising			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
		32	38	39	42.3	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again			at time	14:53:51		

Flight:

B282

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 08/05/2007
18:34:50

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

16/04/2007 18:40:41

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.252**.....

 Date **5/04/2007**.....

 Operator's name: **D. Tideman**.....

 Page **1** of **2**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
								No comms to dry Neph!
1535	R1-1	2.5 kft	13.9		30	20°		
154150		"	13.7			A20°		
154703		"	13.6		46		20°	Humid out 57%
154730			13.			A30°		
155000			13.			A35°		
155100			13.3		61%		35°	Humid at 91.5%
155644			13.5		86.744		35°	" " 86.2%
1558			13.			25°		
161020	R1-2	2.5 kft	13		36		5°	" " 39.1%
161118			13.5			A35°		
161524			13		71.9		35°	" " 92.2%
1624			13			20°		
1700			11.3	-	17%	25°	7°	
171950	R2	1.6 kft	13.9	-	30%	A35°	5°	
172420		"	13.9	-	71.7%	A40°	34.5°	" " 90%
172624		"	13.9	-	84.8	40°	40°	" " 93%
172930		"	13.9	-	86.6	A40°		93.2
174800	R? -	2.5 kft	13.0	-	30.4	25°	9°	33.1
180430	R6-1	1.1 kft	14.0	-	31.2	35°	5°	45

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B282

Date: 15 April 2007

Instruments

1. Noise in Ch. 1 of PCASP
2. Low Ref Voltage on PCASP
3. Flight Manager losing flight Summary and Update Flight Summ windows on regular basis
4. Dry Neph, problems running zero, comms problem
5. Satcom-H appears not to work in the US

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

11 - 3 + 1

Run 1.2 16:02:50

TAPES 16:17:00 changed

SATCOM PROBLEM

16:30 → 16:43 no Cal on H₂O measures, no access to
Denied data - too many plots open by too many
people.

phone satcom, we cut phone out.

P

Plt hrs }
Run 4.1 start } 17:15:39 end 17:16:06.

Plt start 17:16:06
Run 5.1 Start 17:16:26

Run 5.

- WD - 904
- Cap A R
- Co 1A
- Msc 1 - J Taylor
- M 2 - SN
- 3 - AB
- CC - RP
- M51 - W Morgan
- 2 - P W
- w/meph psrp - DT
- CP - Pops
- PM - JT
- Sws - Jeff
- Denso, ~~Avics~~ CH
- Avics - JK

Inmarsat Satcom-C.

- PCASP
- Filt some probs
- dry heph causes problem - No Zero
- SAW HYPERMOTOR - NOT SWITCHED ON TILL IN AIR
- DOUG Y

~~SWAS~~

Mass Ch. 6 as usual

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: **15/4/08**

Flight No: **B292**

Pre-Flighter: **D Angra**

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezovorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> ✓ or ✗	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

Flight B282 18:07:16

Heading 236 deg Speed 205 knots Height 1.1kft Press 972mb

Lat 28°42.0'N Long 94°54.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 314 deg

Temp 9.95C Dewpoint 2.91C

From start to now

Current values
INU LONGITUDE -94.97 deg (+ve E) ● All
CNC COUNTS 34900 p cm-3 ○

New plot, same times

Flight B282 18:05:06

Heading 223 deg Speed 209 knots Height 1.1kft Press 972mb

Lat 28°48.0'N Long 94°48.0'W Wind 9 ms-1/ 323 deg

Temp 10.62C Dewpoint 0.89C

From start to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 65103 secs ● All
CNC COUNTS 58700 p cm-3 ○

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B282:

Log	Reason
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	29 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	31 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Added Stu Newman Mission Scientist 2 log & Cloud Physics Processing log
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x For/Downward Facing Cameras

3 x Upward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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